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**Deliverable: D6.1 – Training plan for in-person training 1 –
Year1**

National Institute for Public Health
and the Environment
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport

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Document overview

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List of Acronyms

AMR	Antimicrobial resistance
DL	Deliverable
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EU	European Union
EURL	EU Reference Laboratory
FWD-Net	European Food- and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses Network
NFP	National Focal Point
NGS	Next-generation Sequencing
OCP	Operational Contact Point
RIVM	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
SSI	Statens Serum Institut
WGS	Whole Genome Sequencing
WP	Work package

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1. General information

This document outlines the training plan for the first in-person training activity of the EURL-PH-FWDB project. This WP aims to develop, organise, and deliver training activities aimed at expanding the knowledge and skills required to improve the current national prevention, preparedness and response plans, in alignment with the training activities of Regulation 2022/2371 on cross-border health threats.

Field	Information
Title of Training	In-person training on basic short-read data analysis, <i>Salmonella</i> serotyping and cluster analysis
Dates	03-06-2026 and 04-06-2026
Duration	Two days
Location	Bilthoven, the Netherlands, RIVM
Organising Institution	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)
Contact Person (name, title, email)	Ninée Buchholtz, scientist, ninee.buchholtz@rivm.nl Train-EURL-PH-FWDB@rivm.nl
Target Audience	Microbiologists and technicians who are interested in the full WGS workflow, from the theoretical laboratory background to cluster analyses. Participants do not need prior experience with WGS.
Number of Participants	25 participants

2. Background and Rationale

Whole genome sequencing (WGS) has become an essential tool for the surveillance and investigation of foodborne pathogens, including *Salmonella*. However, capacities across the EURL-FWD network remain heterogeneous, particularly in relation to bioinformatics analysis and interpretation.

This training addresses identified needs within the network to:

- strengthen technical capacity in WGS-based analysis
- harmonise laboratory and analytical approaches across countries
- support outbreak detection and investigation
- improve data comparability and reporting

The training builds on experience and needs identified through previous initiatives, including FWD AMR-RefLabCap, GenEpi-BioTrain, and relevant EURLs in food safety.

By providing hands-on experience with real datasets and commonly used tools, the course contributes to strengthening national and EU-level preparedness for foodborne outbreak investigations.

3. Training Objectives

3.1 Overall Objective

The objective of this training is to develop practical skills in working with WGS data and to improve understanding of which bioinformatics tools can be used to process short-read sequencing data. These tools will be applied to *Salmonella* serotyping and to demonstrate how cluster analysis can be performed for epidemiological purposes. The training provides participants with stronger capabilities for routine laboratory surveillance and better preparedness for potential outbreak investigations.

3.2 Specific Learning Objectives

After completing the training, participants will be able to:

- Objective 1: Understand the end-to-end workflow from DNA extraction and laboratory procedures for NGS through short-read WGS data analysis for *Salmonella*.
- Objective 2: Perform quality assessment and basic processing of FASTQ files, using hands-on exercises and real datasets.
- Objective 3: Conduct *in silico Salmonella* serotyping by applying the principles of WGS and using selected bioinformatics tools and pipelines to derive a serovar.
- Objective 4: Interpret AMR typing results generated from WGS data using relevant bioinformatics tools.
- Objective 5: Perform basic cluster analysis for outbreak investigation, including running a simple cluster analysis on a resistant *Salmonella* serovar and interpreting results to support outbreak investigations.

4. Target Audience and Participant Profile

The training is intended for:

- microbiologists and laboratory technicians
- staff working at national public health institutes or equivalent laboratories

Participants are expected to:

- have basic experience with *Salmonella* serotyping
- have limited or no prior experience with WGS or bioinformatics
- have sufficient proficiency in English to follow lectures and participate in discussions

The course is designed at an introductory level, progressing from theoretical concepts to hands-on analysis.

5. Training Topics

- Topic 1: Laboratory procedures for the generation of bacterial sequences
- Topic 2: Introduction to bioinformatics WGS for *Salmonella*
- Topic 3: *Salmonella* serotyping using bioinformatics pipelines
- Topic 4: Bioinformatics tools for *Salmonella* AMR typing
- Topic 5: cluster analysis of *Salmonella* and outbreak investigations

6. Training Format and Methodology

The in-person training consists of a two-day course that includes explanatory presentations, followed by workshops with interactive practical exercises. Both the lectures and the workshop supervision will be delivered by internal RIVM EURL-FWD experts. During these workshops, participants will work on real datasets and progress from FASTQ data to a serovar on Day 1 and perform cluster analysis on a resistant *Salmonella* serovar on Day 2. This training is intended for microbiologists and technicians at public health institutes who are involved in *Salmonella* serotyping and WGS and are interested in the full WGS workflow, from theoretical laboratory background to cluster analysis. No prior WGS experience is required, as the course starts at an introductory level.

7. Draft Agenda

Day 1 – 03-06-2026

Time	Session title	Speaker	Format	Location
08:30-09:00	Registration and coffee/tea		Registration	RIVM
09:00-09.15	Welcome and course overview	Ninée Buchholtz	Introduction	RIVM
09:15-10:00	Laboratory procedures for the generation of bacterial sequences	Sjoerd Kuiling	Lecture	RIVM
10:00-10:15	Coffee/tea break		Break	RIVM
10:15-11:15	Introduction to bioinformatics WGS for <i>Salmonella</i>	Casper Jamin	Lecture	RIVM
11:15-12:15	Making assemblies and running a quality control on a <i>Salmonella</i> dataset	To be decided	Workshop	RIVM
12:15-13:15	Lunch		Break	
13:15-14:00	<i>Salmonella</i> serotyping using bioinformatics pipelines	Linda Visser	Lecture	RIVM
14:00-15:30	How to use webtools for <i>Salmonella</i> serotyping	To be decided	Workshop	RIVM
15:30-16:00	Coffee/tea break		Break	RIVM
16:00-16:30	Workshop recap and evaluation	To be decided	Discussion	RIVM
18.30 - 20.00	Dinner			Bilthoven

Day 2 – 04-06-2026

Time	Session title	Speaker	Format	Location
09:30-10:30	Bioinformatics tools for <i>Salmonella</i> AMR typing	Boas van der Putten	Lecture	RIVM
10:30-11:00	Coffee/tea break		Break	RIVM
11:00-12:00	Cluster analysis of <i>Salmonella</i> and outbreak investigations	Epidemiologist	Lecture	RIVM
12:00-13:00	Lunch		Break	RIVM
13:00-14:30	How to perform cluster analysis on a resistant <i>Salmonella</i> serovar	To be decided	Workshop	RIVM
14:30-15:00	Coffee/tea break		Break	RIVM
15:00-15:30	Workshop recap	To be decided	Discussion	RIVM
15:30-16:00	Closing session and evaluation survey	Ninée Buchholtz	Evaluation	RIVM

8. Participant Selection Criteria

The participant should have a professional background as a microbiologist or technician, be employed on a permanent contract, and work for a national public health institute. The participants will be nominated by the NFPs for Food- and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses or OCPs for Microbiology within the EURL Network. Participation of non-NFPs or non-OCPs is possible if they are employed within their respective institutions, i.e. that are staff members of the network laboratories, and their participation will be agreed with ECDC. Basic experience with Salmonella serotyping is expected, while bioinformatics skills are not required. Proficiency in English is essential for effective communication and participation.

9. Invitation Procedure

The invitation will be distributed through the NFPs for Food- and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses and OCPs for Microbiology within the Laboratory Network of the EURL-PH-FWDB.

Each country may nominate two candidates, one primary and one secondary candidate. The secondary candidate may be selected if places remain available or may serve as a reserve for the primary candidate. Participant selection will be carried out by an independent committee of EURL-FWD training organisers, who will assess applications based on predefined criteria.

Applicants will be asked to submit a motivation letter outlining their training needs and the relevance of the course. They will also be required to complete a questionnaire covering their background, experience, role within the national system, and the possibilities for implementing the course at their own institute. Non-NFPs and non-OCPs will be required to submit a letter of support from their NFP or OCP.

The course is expected to accommodate 25 participants. The application deadline is April 17, 2026.

10. Training Evaluation Plan

10.1 Evaluation Objectives

- Assess participant satisfaction
- Assess achievement of learning objectives
- Identify areas for improvement

10.2 Evaluation Methods

After the two-day course, participants are invited to complete an evaluation form in which they can share feedback on each individual element of the course, including the different lectures and workshops, as well as their overall experience. This gives them space to say what worked well, what they felt was missing, and what should definitely remain part of the programme. Training certificates for participation will only be issued to participants who have completed the evaluation form.

10.3 Use of Evaluation Results

The evaluations help support internal quality improvement by showing how participants experienced the different parts of the course and where changes may be needed. In addition, feedback from both participants and the EURL-FWD network can be used to guide adjustments to future trainings, including the selection of topics and the overall design of the programme. The training outcomes and evaluation results will be reported in annual progress report of the EURL.

11. Training Materials and Dissemination

The organiser confirms that:

- All relevant training materials (presentations, exercises, supporting materials and bioinformatic tools) will be made available electronically to the relevant network members after the execution of the training activity.
- Materials will be shared via the [ECON EURL for FWDB collaboration site](#) (NFPs and OCPs) and via email (non-NFPs and non-OCPs)
- Any confidential or restricted materials will be handled according to agreed procedures.

12. Logistical Arrangements

- Course dates:
3 and 4 June 2026
- Venue details and address:
Conference room at the RIVM
Antonie van Leeuwenhoeklaan 9, Bilthoven, The Netherlands
- Technical equipment
Participants are expected to bring their own laptop
- Travel and accommodation arrangements:
Flight tickets will be reimbursed by the organising institute, and hotel accommodations close to the venue will be arranged by the organising institute.
- Catering arrangements
The course will include complimentary coffee and tea, lunch on both days, and dinner on the first day.
- Administrative support
RIVM contact persons will be available for any administrative support

13. Annexes

- Annex 1: Draft Invitation Letter

Annex 1 – Draft Invitation Letter

Dear NFPs for Food- and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses and OCPs for Microbiology,

On behalf of the EURL-PH-FWDB team, we are pleased to invite you to our in-person training programme for 2026.

Training 1: Basic short-read data analysis, Salmonella serotyping and cluster analysis

Date: 3–4 June 2026

Location: National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), Bilthoven, Netherlands

Capacity: 25 participants

The course aims to develop practical skills in working with whole genome sequencing (WGS) data and to improve understanding of bioinformatics tools used to process short-read sequencing data. These tools will be applied to Salmonella serotyping, AMR detection, and to demonstrate how cluster analysis can be performed for epidemiological purposes. The training will strengthen participants' capabilities for routine laboratory surveillance and enhance preparedness for potential outbreak investigations.

Target audience: This training is intended for microbiologists and technicians at public health institutes involved in Salmonella outbreak detections who are interested in the full WGS workflow, from laboratory background to cluster analysis. No prior WGS experience is required, as the course starts at an introductory level.

Travel: Expected arrival on Tuesday the 2nd of June and return to your home country on Thursday 4th of June in the evening.

Training 2: Identification and characterization of pathogenic *Escherichia coli*

Dates:

- Session A: 7–9 September 2026
- Session B: 14–16 September 2026

Location: Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS), Rome, Italy

Capacity: 20 participants (10 per session)

Session A and B are identical. The course aims to develop practical skills to identify and characterise diarrhoeagenic *Escherichia coli*, with a particular focus on Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC).

Target audience: This training is intended for microbiologists and technicians at public health institutes involved in the diagnosis of diarrhoeagenic *E. coli* infections and the characterisation of

STEC and other pathotypes, including Enteroinvasive *E. coli* (EIEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), and Enteroaggregative *E. coli* (EAEC). This course includes practical laboratory exercises.

Travel: Expected arrival on the 7th of September (for session A) and the 14th of September (session B) and return to your home country the 9th of September (session A) and 16th of September (session B).

Application Procedure

Participants are invited to apply for one or both trainings in 2026. Each Member State may nominate up to two candidates per course (one primary and one secondary).

[Link to online application form for Training 1](#)

[Link to online application form for Training 2](#)

The application deadline is **17 April 2026 for both trainings**.

In the application form, candidates are requested to submit:

- A motivation letter describing their role, relevance to the training, and intended use of the skills
- For non-NFP/OCP applicants: a letter of support from the NFP

Soon after, selected participants will be contacted directly and will be provided with practical information about the reservation of flight tickets and accommodation. The EURL-PH-FWDB project will cover the expenses related to travel, accommodation, and per diem.

We look forward to your participation.

On behalf of the EURL-PH-FWDB team

European Union Reference Laboratory for Public Health on Food- and Waterborne Bacteria

General email: Train-EURL-PH-FWDB@ssi.dk

EURL for FWDB collaboration site: [Home](#)

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INSTITUT

National Institute for Public Health
and the Environment
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport

Document review / approval (the coordinator)

Name	Role	Action (review / approval)	Date
David Canovas Jorda	Project officer (HaDEA)	approval	04/05/2026